

Report

High-Power Impulse Magnetron Sputtering (HiPIMS):
Assessing the innovation potential using the Technological
Competence Leveraging (TCL) method

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Abbreviations

CCC	Coating Competence Center
CERN	Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire
FCC	Future Circular Collider
HiPIMS	High-Power Impulse Magnetron Sputtering
LEIR	Low Energy Ion Ring
LHC	Large Hadron Collider
PECVD	Plasma-Enhanced Chemical Vapour Deposition
PS	Proton Synchrotron
PVD	Physical Vapor Deposition
TCL	Technology Competence Leveraging
µm	Micrometers
µs	Microseconds

Executive Summary

Project overview

High-Power Impulse Magnetron Sputtering (HiPIMS) is an advanced coating technology that is currently being further developed for manufacturing superconducting radiofrequency cavities of particle accelerators. Although this technology offers numerous benefits compared to common coating techniques, the number of industrial applications is today still low. This leads to slow adoption of the technology, further developments and high costs of HiPIMS coatings. The aim of this project, therefore, is to identify and analyse potential application fields for HiPIMS to ultimately increase industrial adoption of this technology.

Methodology

First, a technology description outlines the technological aspects of the project by giving an overview of HiPIMS and its important characteristics. 30 interviews with leading experts of HiPIMS and literature research are the sources of information.

The following part, on which this project focuses on, follows the methodology of Technology Competence Leveraging. This systematic four-step approach is an effective method to identify potential application fields for existing technologies without the need for technical in-depth knowledge. The objectives and sub-goals of the TCL method are (1) the identification of the core benefits of the technology, (2) discovering potential application fields with a need for these benefits, (3) analyzing the possible alternative industries and (4) the development of a profound exploitation strategy for the technology (Keinz and Prügl, 2010). Since the scope of this project focuses on the first three steps, the fourth step of the Technology Competence Leveraging method is not included. The theoretical methods and tools pyramiding, brainstorming, expert interviews and customer discovery interviews as well as the extensive knowledge of user communities are used to gather information.

Results

The expert and current user interviews conducted as part of the first step resulted in three core benefits of HiPIMS. They are used as the foundation for the next step, identifying potential application fields.

- (1) Possibility to coat complex 3D-structures**
- (2) Thinner and more precise coatings**
- (3) Longer lasting and durable coatings**

Based on these core benefits 9 industries comprising 28 potential application fields are identified by using individual and group brainstorming and utilizing specified user communities. The most promising application fields are evaluated by assessing the so-called Benefit relevance and Strategic fit, which

combined result in an overall score that indicates the fit between HiPIMS, the needs and constraints of CERN and the respective application field. This analysis lead to four promising application fields.

(1) Ski equipment

The upper side of the ski is exposed to many different conditions. The current protection with a plastic foil is not satisfactory. Therefore, a coating with HiPIMS is a possibility to make the skis more resistant and therefore longer usable for the customer. It leads to a reputation increase for the ski manufacturer.

(2) Prostheses & Stents

HiPIMS could be used to coat sensitive medical devices such as prostheses and stents. Coatings with high wear off-resistance and a high degree of sterility, due to the dense coatings achieved with HiPIMS, could greatly increase the durability and functionality of those medical devices. Since the medical industry requires a high reliability of instruments, HiPIMS shows potential to set quality standards.

(3) Industrial stamping tools

Industrial stamping tools have to endure high degrees of mechanical stress and are required to have maximized service lives. The hard and wear off-resistant layers achieved with HiPIMS could therefore increase precision of industrial stamping tools while increasing the number of possible strokes at the same time. These tools are used in a variety of industries and are mostly used to manufacture components in high volumes, which underlines the need for highly sophisticated product characteristics.

(4) Food manufacturing machinery

The process of manufacturing food is bound to high quality standards. Especially, painted components of machines with no direct food contact and parts of these machines with direct food contact have a variety of deficits that bear risks. HiPIMS coatings could be used for these components to extend their lifetime, increase safety of food production and improve the level of hygiene of surfaces.

1 Project partner

The *Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire* (CERN) is a world leading research organization focusing mainly on the field of understanding better the fundamental principles that govern our Universe. It was founded in 1954 with the main mission to deepen the knowledge about and the understanding of how particles interact with each other on an elementary level. The results of the organization's research are made available publicly free of charge (CERN, 2019).

The organization has today twenty-three member states, each of which has two official delegates to the CERN Council. Its facilities are run by about 2,500 technical, scientific and administrative staff members and over 12,000 associated external members that conduct research (CERN, 2019).

CERN operates the world's largest complex of particle accelerators. The most powerful scientific instrument is a particle accelerator called Large Hadron Collider (LHC). It has a length of 26.7 km and runs in a circular shaped underground tunnel. Using sophisticated technologies like superconducting magnets chilled to temperatures near absolute zero and radiofrequency cavities, particles are accelerated close to the speed of light. After the particles have reached their target speed, they collide with each other (CERN, 2019). This process is then tracked by detectors to gather data about the collision which is used to get a better understanding of the fundamental constituents of matter (ATLAS, 2019).

The LHC, however, is not the only instrument available for scientists at CERN. There are several other particle accelerators like the Low Energy Ion Ring (LEIR), the Proton Synchrotron (PS) and the Antiproton Decelerator.

Figure 1 - Scientific instruments at CERN (Hunter, 2017)

Since the Large Hadron Collider does not meet the needs of future research, CERN is currently planning to build a bigger “Future Circular Collider” (FCC). With a proposed length of about 100 km the FCC would be substantially larger than the existing LHC and thus, one of the major challenges will be the high demand for resources both, natural and financial (CERN, 2019).

2 Project description

Within the scope of EASITrain, a H2020 project funded by the EU, multiple projects have been conducted for the FCC project at Vienna University of Economics and Business. The focus of these previous efforts was on finding alternative applications for technologies needed in the manufacturing process of superconducting magnets and analyzing the most promising application fields. This project constitutes a follow-up project that aims to help CERN lower the costs for their planned Future Circular Collider, which is meant to take over from the LHC and extend its research. The following paragraphs define the scope, challenges and objectives of the project.

2.1 Problem definition

In order to conduct their experiments, scientists at CERN rely on sophisticated components like powerful superconducting magnets and radiofrequency cavities. Due to the size of the FCC, it requires considerable amounts of these parts. Therefore, the construction of the FCC needs concerted value-engineering of each component (CERN COURIER, 2019).

This project focuses on the radiofrequency (RF) cavities, which are used to accelerate the particles. So far, these cavities are built using pure Niobium, which represents a substantial cost factor. To achieve significant savings in material costs CERN is planning to produce cavities using the High-Power Impulse Magnetron Sputtering (HiPIMS) technology to coat copper with a thin layer of superconducting material, which would result in lower costs. The problem is that High-Power Impulse Magnetron Sputtering is not commonly used in industrial manufacturing. This means low competition, too little experience and high prices for such coatings.

2.2 Objectives

The primary objective of this project is to identify and analyze new promising application fields for HiPIMS in various industries, making FCC an example of “Open Innovation”, i.e. the dissemination of novel technologies with high societal value that are pioneered in the context of large-scale high-tech projects for fundamental science. The diffusion of this technology is meant to cause higher competition and increased experience in industry and therefore result in lower costs and constant quality for such coatings. One essential step to achieve this is to determine the core benefits it provides for its current users. Based on these findings, the subsequent objective is to identify potential application fields. All in all, **this project will help to disseminate the knowledge about the benefits of HiPIMS technology in the society, which will benefit involved manufacturers and CERN alike and contribute to public welfare.**

3 Methodology

The analytical section of this report is divided into four main parts – (1) a technology description, (2) the analysis of the core benefits, (3) the identification of potential application fields and (4) finally the in-depth analysis of the most promising application fields.

In order to gain information and analyze the gathered output we use a variety of methods. Therefore, the aim of this chapter is to give an outline of the used methods in order to provide an overview of the approach. The first part covers the description of the involved technologies. Afterwards, the Technology Competence Leveraging method is explained in detail to get an understanding of how results are derived.

3.1 Technology description

The technology description outlines fundamental components and technologies which are relevant for this project. It focuses on the radiofrequency cavities in general and HiPIMS, which is the technology used to coat them.

Data is collected in a two-step approach. First, extensive literature research is conducted to get a profound information base. Second, aspects mentioned during the interviews will be used to complement the secondary data. Therefore, both primary and secondary data is used to guarantee comprehensive information on HiPIMS.

3.2 Technology Competence Leveraging

The methodology used to find potential application fields for HiPIMS is the Technology Competence Leveraging (TCL) method. This systematic approach is used to efficiently determine potential application fields without the need to acquire in-depth technological knowledge. The method consists of four consecutive steps that have to be completed sequentially. The objectives and sub-goals of the TCL method are (1) the identification of the core benefits of a technology, (2) discovering potential application fields with a need for these benefits, (3) analyzing the possible alternative industries and (4) the development of a profound exploitation strategy for the technology (Keinz and Prügl, 2010). This project focuses mainly on the identification of the core benefits and the determination and analysis of new application fields.

3.2.1 Identification of the core benefits

The goal of this step is to get an understanding of the created value of the technology (Keinz and Prügl, 2010). Hence, the first step is the identification of the core benefits of HiPIMS. They serve as the foundation for the subsequent steps as they enable to find more distant application fields in which the use of HiPIMS and the characteristics of its coatings might cater to similar needs. For this purpose, ten interviews with current users and researchers with expertise in HiPIMS are held to generate a sufficient amount of information to identify the three core benefits of HiPIMS (Keinz, 2019).

Semi-structured interviews are used to encourage discussions and examine special features in greater detail during the interviews (Cohen, 2006). This means that no exact predefined guideline is developed and open-ended questions regarding the benefits are asked. Results of previously held interviews are mentioned during the conversations in order to get more detailed insights and verify previous findings. The summaries including the most important aspects mentioned by the interviewees are included in Appendix A (p. xii).

Interviewees are found through online research and pyramiding, beginning with engineers of CERN. Pyramiding is a search strategy that is based on the assumption that people with expertise in a given field often know someone who knows even more about it than they do (Hippel et al., 2009). Thus, after conducting interviews, the interviewees are asked for contact details of additional experts. The gathered information of the interviews is then complemented by findings of research papers analyzing HiPIMS and its benefits.

3.2.2 Identification of alternative application fields

The identified core benefits of HiPIMS form the basis for the subsequent search for potential application fields, for which HiPIMS might be of interest. The search is not limited to specific industries or application areas. On the contrary, it aims at finding previously unknown and unnoticed application potentials. The result of this step is a list of application fields that have a basic need for the core benefits of HiPIMS. A combination of several methods is used to identify potential application fields including brainstorming, online communities and customer discovery interviews.

First, an advanced brainstorming technique that combines elements of individual and group brainstorming is used. This creativity technique is a two-step approach that prevents common issues of conventional group brainstorming and enhances the effectiveness of individual brainstorming (Brown and Paulus, 2002). First, the project team brainstorms together to get as much initial input as possible. Then the individuals of the team have time to brainstorm on their own without any disruption. The selected industries and application fields are then clustered into groups. In order to get high homogeneity within clusters and high heterogeneity between them, the classification of the application fields is based on the industries they belong to and on similarities of industrial production processes.

Subsequently, online communities are consulted and the knowledge of its users are leveraged through posts asking for application possibilities of HiPIMS in their industries. This is done to verify previously brainstormed potential application fields and get additional information.

Finally, based on the list of the previously brainstormed application fields 20 customer discovery interviews are held to obtain profound knowledge about the applicability of HiPIMS in the respective application fields. Of the 20 interview partners, four preferred to stay anonymous and are thus anonymized throughout the report. Pyramiding is used to identify experts in these areas who could contribute to the determination of the fit of HiPIMS for their industry. Industries that prove unsuitable

after the customer discovery interviews are excluded and not analysed. An industry's is deemed as unsuitable if its benefit relevance or strategic fit score is low. Its specific calculation is further explained in the following part.

3.2.3 Relevance evaluation

In this step, previously identified promising application fields are evaluated to examine the applicability of HiPIMS for the respective field. By taking the industry specific benefit relevance and the internal strategic orientation of CERN into account, the overall relevance of a potential application field is determined. The two factors are further referred to as Benefit relevance and Strategic fit. These two factors are used to assess the applicability of HiPIMS in potential application fields.

Benefit relevance

The Benefit relevance is a measure that indicates how beneficial a technology is for a potential application field. By its definition, the Benefit relevance combines the number of relevant core benefits that were previously identified and their relative importance within a specific application field (Keinz and Prügl, 2010). This relative importance is referred to as relevance index in the formula (1) Benefit relevance below. It constitutes a value that specifies the need of the respective industry for the benefits of HiPIMS. The data to determine the relevance index is collected in the customer discovery interviews. Therefore, at the end of every customer discovery interview the potential customer answers the four relevance index items, according to the specific industry. The items are equally weighted and assessed through a 3-Point-Item-Likert-Scale. Whenever the interviewee does absolutely agree with the stated item, two points are used for the further calculation. If the interviewee is not entirely convinced, but partly agrees with an item, one point is used for the further calculation. If the interviewee does not share the believe or expects very low occurrence probability for the specific item, zero points are used for the further calculation. Next, the points given by the potential customer are added up and divided by the factor four to generate the relevance index. Eventually, the generated relevance index is multiplied by the factor of relevant benefits. The factor of relevant benefits is defined as decimal number resulting from the number of relevant benefits for a specific application field divided by the number of defined core benefits. For every application field, the identified Benefit relevance is used to determine the value HiPIMS could add to it.

The following formula demonstrates how the Benefit relevance is calculated:

$$(1) \text{ Benefit relevance} = \frac{\text{number of relevant benefits}}{\text{number of defined benefits}} * \text{relevance index}$$

The relevance index is defined by the following items which are weighted equally at 25 percent each:

- The problem is relevant
- The problem will become more important in the future
- The prevailing solution is not sufficient
- The solution is important for a high number of people

The quantification of the items is based on a 3-Point-Item-Likert-Scale.

- 0 = false or low
- 1 = partly right or medium
- 2 = right or high

Strategic fit

Strategic fit is measured by the needs and restrictions of CERN, which should be reflected in potential fields of application. Thus, it is used as an indicator of adequacy of a specific application field and CERN's strategic orientation. The project partner has declared four needs and requests, which are used as guiding principles and restrictions for further exploration. Moreover, these indicators (all four indicators are mentioned below) are used to quantify the Strategic Fit parameter. Therefore, the calculated parameter is used to conclude the evaluation of identified potential application fields. Application fields that are in conflict with the values and objectives of CERN such as military application fields have no Strategic fit and are not taken into account. An alignment between CERN's declared guidelines and the application field is crucial for further examination.

In order to ensure the inclusion of all important Strategic fit factors, the following items were determined in consultation with CERN:

- **Regionality of the products industry** (European Union; preferred DACH area)
- **Size of the parts** to be coated is **similar to CERN's cavities** (diameter: 40cm, length: 100-200cm)
- **Further improvement** of the HiPIMS technology will be **facilitated by users**
- **Market Fit** (New field of application shows high market potential)

The quantification of the items is based on a 3-Point-Item-Likert-Scale:

- 0 = false or low
- 1 = partly right or medium
- 2 = right or high

Moreover, there is one restriction which lead to an immediate **exclusion of further examination**:

- **Military related areas of application**

The Strategic Fit calculation is defined as follows:

$$(2) \text{ Strategic fit} = \frac{\text{regionality} + \text{size} + \text{technology improvement} + \text{market fit}}{4}$$

Whenever the items fully comply, two points are allocated for the further calculation. For instance, the entire value creation process of a product, including its manufacturing, takes place in Germany. The example meets the requirement of regionality (DACH area). If the does not entirely comply, but shows similar attributes to the specific item, one point is allocated for further calculation. For instance, the size of the parts to be coated is not similar, but shows only 10 percent more in length. Another example for a partly met regionality requirement can be demonstrated by the value creation process separated within a global supply chain. If only about 50% of its value is captured within Europe, the requirement of regionality is only partly met. If the items stated requirement is not met at all, zero points are allocated for further calculation. This can be observed for instance, whenever none of the created value is captured within the European Union's area.

In the following paragraph the items “Further improvement of HiPIMS” and “Market fit” are explained in further detail. First, “Further improvement of the HiPIMS technology will be facilitated by users” is examined. Whenever the coating process within a specific industry accounts for a large part of its manufacturing or value creation process and when the industry produces high volumes, further improvements of the technology can be anticipated. Therefore, large suppliers in the car industry manufacturing parts of vehicle chassis frames can be mentioned. Another indicator for further improvements is the amount of investment in R&D in industries. Meeting such requirements lead to the allocation of two points. If only some of those qualifications are met, one point is given. For example, if the coating process accounts for a large part of the value creation, but the industry does not manufacture in high volume, or high volume is produced but the coating process only accounts for a little part of the manufacturing or value creation process, the HiPIMS technology’s further improvement cannot be anticipated without uncertainty. If none of the qualifications mentioned above are met, the probability of further improvement is anticipated as very low. Hence, zero points are assigned.

Second, the item “Market fit” is introduced in more detail. The item quantifies the market potential of a specific industry as a quantified number. In order to measure the market potential in a basic way, we focus on three factors: the potential customer base, the competition and the current environmental and economic conditions that may affect the market potential. Because of these three factors, the market fit constitutes a parameter of its own, using the prior used 3-Point-Item-Likert-Scale quantification for the

factors. Whenever a company shows a high potential customer base, for example the automotive industry, two points are allocated. If the customer base is relatively low, one or zero points are given. Similarly, allocated are the points regarding a market's competition. If a market shows rather high competition, its industry potential profitability is deemed as low. If a market shows low or no competition, the potential of the industry is deemed as high. This basic assumption is adopted by Michael Porter's Five Forces Model for the assessment of an industry's profitability. Another factor are the current environmental and economic conditions, which are usually not specific for one industry when the market works properly. However, if single markets are unstable or seem to face a recession, it becomes a more or less independent industry specific issue. If a market struggles or is expected to struggle in the near future, zero points are allocated, due to low further market growth. Market failure can take different forms such as "Dieselgate", the Volkswagen emissions scandal, in 2015. Due to the final objective, the recommendation of a high-quality ranking of the most promising potential application fields, absolute numbers will be provided within these chapters. Similarly, to the other calculation, the three allocated points are added up and divided by three to generate the accurate Market fit parameter.

The Market fit parameter is defined as follows:

$$(3) \quad \text{Market fit} = \frac{\text{customer base} + \text{competition} + \text{environmental situation}}{3}$$

The quantification of the Market fit items is based on a 3-Point-Item-Likert-Scale:

- 0 = low / bad
- 1 = medium / satisfactory
- 2 = high / good

Next, the given points are added up and divided by the factor four to generate the Strategic fit parameter.

The accurate assessment of Benefit relevance and Strategic fit parameters in evaluating potential application fields is crucial for high-quality recommendations. The higher the scores of these parameters are, the better HiPIMS is suited for the potential application field.

While the detailed theoretical information about Benefit relevance and Strategic fit is discussed in the methodology chapter, the final graphic visualization of potential application fields and their respective parameters can be found in the analysis chapter.

3.2.4 Industry overview

Building a profound commercialization strategy requires an analysis of the application fields. Therefore, the four most promising application fields are identified according to their overall score and analyzed in detail. Information is gathered from 20 customer discovery interviews with representatives of companies in various industries. For each of the four application fields we, subsequently describe the concrete problem which can be solved, the market potential and potential companies that could benefit from implementing HiPIMS (Keinz and Prügl, 2010). This offers a short overview for possible future exploitation strategies.

3.3 Milestone plan

To guarantee efficient and structured progress, a milestone plan has been made. It provides an overview of the most important steps. A more detailed description of each step and its specific parts can be found above.

Figure 2 - Milestone plan (Fuchs, 2019)

4 Analysis

This chapter presents the findings of the project. The technology description at the beginning of this chapter examines the underlying technologies of the project to give the reader an overview. The subsequent chapter on the core benefits of HiPIMS includes our findings derived from the expert interviews. In the following chapter potential application fields of HiPIMS are identified and analysed.

4.1 Technology description

To conduct their experiments, scientists at CERN rely on powerful superconducting magnets and radiofrequency cavities. The development and manufacturing of these components require high investments in R&D and the use of high-tech manufacturing technologies. In the following sections, the radiofrequency (RF) cavities and High Power Impulse Magnetron Sputtering (HiPIMS), which is used to coat the radiofrequency cavities, are described.

4.1.1 Radiofrequency cavities

The complex system of radiofrequency cavities forms a substantial component of the LHC, as these parts are used to accelerate particles close to the speed of light. The cavities, consequently, function as the engine of the particle accelerator. The metal chamber-shaped RF cavities house the beam pipe, in which the particles travel in a vacuum. The structure of the cavities can be depicted like beads on a string. Inside the cavities strong electromagnetic fields are induced, which oscillate at a specific frequency (each cavity in the LHC oscillates at precisely 400 MHz). When charged particles are sent through the cavities, they interact with the magnetic field resulting in a steady acceleration (CERN, 2012).

Figure 3 - Graphical illustration of the functionality of an RF cavity (Cenni, 2019)

In order to efficiently create and maintain such powerful magnetic fields, radiofrequency cavities use low-temperature superconductivity. The cavities, therefore, must be built using superconducting materials and must be cooled to temperatures close to absolute zero. Today the material of choice is pure

Niobium as it is relatively easy to form and features the needed superconductive characteristics. With a price of about 42,000 USD per metric ton (Metalary, 2018), Niobium represents a considerable cost factor in the production of the cavities. As CERN is planning on building the even bigger FCC particle accelerator in the next decades, these costs could result in constraints on the project.

Therefore, engineers at CERN have been working on solutions to save money on materials while retaining the properties of bulk superconducting cavities for the last decades. The currently pursued idea is to coat relatively cheap copper – about 5,700 USD per metric ton (LME, 2020) - with a thin layer of Niobium. Some prototypes have already been developed and the initial deployment in small particle accelerators have shown promising results (Langner et al., 2005).

Figure 4 - RF cavities before and after the coating process (CERN COURIER, 2019)

4.1.2 High Power Impulse Magnetron Sputtering (HiPIMS)

High Power Impulse Magnetron Sputtering (HiPIMS) is a coating technique that is used in the manufacturing of thin-film radiofrequency cavities needed for the LHC and the proposed FCC.

Although Mr. Eichenhofer, an expert in the field of plasma power solutions for thin-film processing, indicated that HiPIMS had already been in development in the former Soviet Union during the late 1980s, the technology was first patented in 1999 by the Russian Vladimir Kouznetsov. Since then it has become increasingly popular amongst scientists and the number of industrial applications is growing steadily (Hughes, 2014).

HiPIMS is an advancement of the widely used Magnetron Sputtering technique which still shares a lot of common features. In both cases the substrate (the material to be coated) and the target material (the coating material) are placed inside a vacuum chamber filled with an inert gas. A negative charge is then applied to the target material, which causes electrons to flow to the positively charged substrate. On their way they collide with the atoms of the inert gas causing them to become positively charged ions. These

Figure 5 - Process of HiPIMS coating (Hughes, 2016)

ions are then attracted by the negative target material and hit the target at a very high speed resulting in the knockout of atomic size particles of the target material. These particles then cross the vacuum chamber and are deposited as a thin film on the surface of the substrate (Hughes, 2014).

The main difference between HiPIMS and ordinary Magnetron Sputtering is the power supply unit of the coating chamber. An ordinary Magnetron Sputtering machine can be converted to a HiPIMS device by exchanging the power supply unit. The required power unit is associated with costs of about 30,000 € but the variable costs are the same for both technologies (Eichenhofer, 2019). While Magnetron Sputtering uses a constant flow of energy with a steady voltage, HiPIMS utilizes short bursts of energy ($\sim 100 \mu\text{s}$) with a high voltage. This results in a higher degree of ionization of the target material without overheating and the creation of a denser plasma cloud inside the chamber (Hughes, 2016).

HiPIMS is superior to the standard Magnetron Sputtering in several ways. As the average temperature during the coating process is lower than with Magnetron Sputtering HiPIMS can be used to coat temperature sensitive materials and objects like semiconductors and plastics (Eichenhofer, 2019). In addition, it also works well at high temperatures, which means high melting point materials can also be coated properly (Pira, 2019).

Moreover, according to Günter Mark, CEO of Melec GmbH, a HiPIMS machines manufacturing company (2020), HiPIMS allows coatings with various materials. Transparent coatings for example are possible by coating the substrate material with silicon dioxide. Water repellent coatings are also possible and could be of major interest for solar panel manufacturers.

Attributes of HiPIMS such as high layer-structure density, high corrosion-resistance and high coating adhesion strength are other major benefits over ordinary Magnetron Sputtering. HiPIMS, therefore,

makes it possible to produce even smoother and cleaner surfaces (Münz, 2016). Furthermore, HiPIMS combines the high surface quality achieved with regular Magnetron Sputtering with being able to produce a similar high-density film like cathodic coating.

Another point worth mentioning is that the bombardment of the substrate with high energy ions removes the natural oxide layer of the material which allows for the use of HiPIMS as an efficient pretreatment. This cleansing treatment can increase the adhesion of the coating on the substrate (Hughes, 2016).

One major drawback, however, is the occasional appearance of so-called light arcs. These arcs are the result of power discharges, when voltages get too high. Heavy arcing can lead to overheating of the target material and the ejection of microdroplets, which in turn lead to problems with the uniform film growth (Hughes, 2016).

Current application fields

Interviews and literature research have resulted in the identification of five distinct fields where HiPIMS with its respective benefits is currently used:

- tool industry (cutters, hammers, drills)
- automotive industry
- optical industry (glasses, sunglasses, binoculars)
- glass industry (windowpanes, functional coating)
- medical technology (pacemakers, brain pacemakers, implants)

However, according to Mark (2020) the industrial adoption rate is still low. So far HiPIMS is only used in the tool industry on a regular basis. He also stated that only between 15% and 20% of all tools are coated using HiPIMS. Furthermore, there is only a limited number (according to Mark only 5-6) of plant manufacturers in Europe that offer HiPIMS coating machinery or HiPIMS coating services, with CEMECON, Oerlikon Balzers and IHI Hauzer being the biggest ones.

In the other four sectors, it is used to a very limited degree or is currently being tested. Therefore, no clear separation between current and potential application fields can be drawn.

4.2 Core benefits

For the first step of the TCL method ten experts and current users have been interviewed and four scientific papers have been analyzed. Based on the gathered data, seven use benefits have been determined and derived from the process' features and defined as specific advantages compared to other existing coating techniques.

Interviewee	Use Benefits						
	Longer service life due to better durability	Better surface quality of the coated material	Possibility to coat complex three-dimensional shapes	Possibility to coat more diverse substrates	Variability of the degree of ionization	Less scraps produced during the process	Improved electrical conductivity
Bandorf, R. (Fraunhofer)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Eichenhofer, G. (4A-Plasma)	X	X	X	X			
Mark, G. (Melec)	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Pira, C. (INFN)	X	X					
Garcia Diaz, V. (INFN)	X	X		X			
Thorwarth, K. (CCC)		X	X	X			
Leith, S. (Univ. Siegen)	X	X	X	X	X		
Fonnesu, D. (CERN)	X		X				
Schiffers, C. (CemeCon)	X	X	X	X			
Vogel, M. (Univ. Siegen)	X	X	X	X			
Mentions:	9	9	8	8	3	2	1

Table 1 - User Benefits (Grech, 2019)

In consultation with Dr. Peter Keinz, professor at the Vienna University of Economics and Business and expert for the TCL method, the benefits that relate to the same characteristic were combined and brought to a higher level of abstraction. Subsequently, generalized terms were formulated to name the core benefits in a universally understandable way. This process has resulted in three core benefits of HiPIMS depicted in figure 6.

Possibility to coat complex 3D-structures

Thinner, more precise coatings

Longer lasting coatings

Figure 6 - Figure 6 - Core Benefits (Fuchs, 2019)

4.2.1 Possibility to coat complex 3D-structures

The first core benefit is that **complex three-dimensional parts can be coated precisely**. Coating **corners, edges** and parts **with holes and excavations** is possible with HiPIMS. This makes it feasible to coat workpieces with a high level of **continuity and uniformity** (Eichenhofer, 2019). Accurate coatings on the complexly shaped insides of radiofrequency cavities demonstrate this characteristic vividly. This means that the search for new fields of application is not limited to any physical form of the product to be coated, which is a major advantage in comparison to common coating technologies that are restricted to shapes of lower complexity.

Furthermore, with the HiPIMS method it is not only possible to coat complex structures, but also various materials. This makes it possible to coat, for instance, **semiconductors and plastics**, which are often produced in complex physical shapes (Eichenhofer, 2019). What is more, 3D-shaped glass and plastics can be processed with remarkable results in quality of film surface, as there are no restrictions of physical shape and there is sufficient performance at lower substrate temperatures (Eichenhofer, Fernandez, Wennberg, 2017).

4.2.2 Longer-lasting coatings

The second core benefit determined, is the possibility to create **longer-lasting** coatings. This benefit derives from the high variability of the degree of ionization, which allows **harder** coatings than common coating techniques achieve, and the high surface quality of HiPIMS coatings. This attribute makes coated products more **durable**, especially **when exposed to mechanical stress or high friction**. Thus, one step further into consumers' applications, advantages are for example, **less friction** with pistons and engine parts, which leads to better performance and longer lifetime of those products (Bandorf, 2019).

Furthermore, in the professional journal "Galvanotechnik" (2016) the following characteristics of a HiPIMS coated surface were specified: high **wearing-resistance**, high **corrosion-resistance** and immense **coating adhesion strength** (Münz, 2016).

4.2.3 Thinner, more precise and versatile coatings

The possibility to coat **thinner** and **more precisely** was mentioned frequently by the interviewed experts. Those, thin HiPIMS coatings offer better properties in terms of **corrosion resistance** than thicker coatings made with common techniques. U. Helmersson demonstrated in an experiment in 2006 that HiPIMS coatings with the thickness of 2 μm have a better corrosion resistance than 20- μm -thick hard chrome coatings. HiPIMS coatings also have a very **low level of internal tensions** (Schiffers, 2019). Thin layers can thus endure high mechanical stress.

With the advantage of being able to produce thinner layers, HiPIMS is not only a very precise surface coating method, but also an **environmentally friendly** technology. By using considerably less coating material than its alternatives, using the HiPIMS method leads to savings on coating material, and therefore, also to savings in terms of costs (Helmersson, 2006).

Due to the high quality of the coated surface, the technology can be applied in fields such as **long-lasting antibacterial coatings** (e.g. medical linens, surgical instruments, partition walls or even doorknobs and handles for water faucets in sensitive amicrobic areas) (Eichenhofer, Fernandez, Wennberg, 2017). The application in the medical field shows therefore high potential. Also the study published in the Environmental Science and Pollution Research brought interesting results in terms of HiPIMS thin-film depositions and their bacterial inactivation capabilities (Ehiasarian, Pulgarin, Kiwi, 2012).

4.3 Identification of potential application fields

This chapter covers the identification of potential application fields for HiPIMS based on the use benefits. It includes findings from initial brainstorming that was used to identify industries that could benefit through the implementation of HiPIMS. Furthermore, this chapter covers includes the clustering of related application fields, the leveraging of user communities focusing on these specific potential application fields and findings from customer discovery interviews.

4.3.1 Idea Generation

In order to identify diverse and non-obvious application fields, individual and group brainstorming is used. This creative technique reduces common issues of traditional group brainstorming while achieving more diverse results (Brown and Paulus, 2002).

The brainstorming focuses on two aspects - on the one hand on application fields that could fit because of the identified core benefits and on the other hand on analogous industries of application fields where HiPIMS is used.

Since the search is not limited to any specific industries or application areas, 28 potential application fields were identified.

In order to guarantee efficient progress throughout the customer discovery interviews, the brainstormed application fields were clustered. Not focusing on too specific application fields at the beginning allows to cover a broader range of different application fields.

Figure 7 - Clustered application fields (Zsilavec, 2020)

4.3.2 Verification

In order to get initial knowledge about the applicability of HiPIMS in the clustered application fields, user communities were used. Postings in such communities that unite people with profound expertise in these areas were made to get an initial assessment of HiPIMS for their respective field. Details on the user communities that were approached can be found in Appendix C.

4.3.2 Selection

As part of the TCL Method, the next step, before starting further potential industry examinations, is the selection of the most promising industries and the rejection of less promising application fields (Keinz, 2019). In this selection process we based our groups' decision for the 10 most promising industries on two factors. First, the project partners mentioned aspects of importance like the product size and its value and secondly, on recommendations and knowledge obtained in the conducted expert interviews.

4.4 High potential industries

In the following section, an overview of the high potential industries for the application of HiPIMS is provided.

4.4.1 Assessment of application fields

Figure 8 - Assessment of application fields (Fuchs, 2020)

Based on the information and data gathered in the customer discovery interviews, the Benefit relevance and Strategic fit of each respective application field was calculated. Both scores were added up and subsequently ranked according to their overall score. Detailed information on the composition and formula of both factors can be found in the methodology chapter. The calculations for each application field are described in Appendix D. Figure 8 depicts the potential of the evaluated application fields based on their Benefit relevance and Strategic fit. The bubbles are of different sizes to enable a better differentiation between medium-potential and high-potential application fields.

Based on their high overall score, ski equipment, prostheses and stents, industrial punching tools and food manufacturing machinery were selected as high potential application fields and subsequently evaluated according to their relevance and market potential.

4.4.2 Ski equipment

According to Mr. Helmut Holzer, Director of Anticipation & Advanced Research at Atomic Austria GmbH, the coating of the upper side of the ski is a very interesting and innovative topic. Atomic is part of Amer Sports, which is a key manufacturer in the field of ski equipment (Technavio, 2016).

Figure 9 - Atomic Race Carver (Atomic, 2020)

Problem description

The upper side of a ski is exposed to many different strains:

On the one hand, it has to withstand temperatures between -30 and +100 degrees Celsius, and on the other hand it is exposed to high levels of UV radiation. The surface is exposed to immense pressure and stress during skiing itself. In addition, the ski and its surface must be flexible and bendable in order to achieve the best possible results. Furthermore, the optical aspect should not be neglected, because both the emblem of the manufacturer and the general design of the ski can be seen here (Holzer, 2020).

The current problem is on the one hand that the colours and logos fade away and the whole ski turns greyish. This reduces the recognition value and the optical appearance of the ski very much.

Current solutions

The most common method is to apply a thin plastic foil made of polyamide or TPU (thermoplastic polyurethane elastomers) is attached to protect the surface. A solution using a special coating method is currently not available. According to Holzer (2020) the current foil which covers the ski on the upper side is fading off relatively easily, which means that after a certain point the ski itself can be damaged (Holzer, 2020, Anonymous 3, 2020).

Potential of the technology within the application field

Due to the urgent need for a solution, the potential is very high. Mr. Helmut Holzer from Atomic and our other interviewee rated the urgency 8 out of 10. With HiPIMS, ski manufacturers can coat the upper side of the ski with a transparent coating, which would greatly increase the wear resistance. There are currently no comparable solutions available, therefore HiPIMS has the chance to take a pioneering role in this market. Furthermore, HiPIMS could be a potential solution also for the coating of snowboards, wakeboards and water-skis.

Restrictions and need for adaptation

One possible restriction is to use a material for coating, which will not contaminate the snow or damage the mountains in general. The costs of the adaption to a coated surface of the ski are the acquisition costs of a coating machine and the coating material. Another point worth mentioning is that with the coating the whole production cycle of a pair of skis is longer than it used to be (Holzer, 2020, Anonymous 3,

2020). At the moment coating the base of the ski does not seem promising as the available options exceed the advantages of an HiPIMS coating,

Benefit Relevance and Strategic Fit

The Benefit relevance is considerably high. Two out of the three main benefits (possibility to coat complex 3D-structures and longer lasting coatings) would be very useful in this context. Furthermore, the relevance of the index influencing variables was high, whereas the probability that this problem will become even more significant in the future is considerably low. In the end this adds up to a Benefit relevance score of 1.17 out of 2.

The strategic fit in this industry is ranked at the top. The regionality is very high, as almost all major ski producers come from Europe and produce a large part of their products in Europe. The length of the skis is quite comparable to the length of the cavities, which is why the fit has a score of 2 out of 2 here as well. The users will also drive the development themselves, as some of the development enthusiasts are lead users here, which we have already discovered through our forum entries. The market potential is very large, as this is a mass market that lives continuously from innovations and the right coating would be an additional advantage.

Altogether this adds up to a high score of 3.17 index points.

Market Overview and Data

In 2018 global ski sales generated over 300 million EUR in revenues and the market has shown constant growth rates since 2016. In the winter of 2017, sales of skis and ski boots rose almost 10 percent. In 2019, almost 20 percent more ski sales were registered than in 2016 (Statista, 2019).

Table 2 - Sales figures of skis and snowboards in 2018 (in Million units) (Statista, 2019)

A closer look at the market shows its high range in product prices, with discounter products starting at pair prices about 100 EUR, a high-quality segment, starting at pair prices about 400 EUR and a luxury segment with virtually no price limits. Especially with competitive race ski and luxury ski quality is more important than price. However, the medium to high price segment shows the biggest sales volume. Especially sales in the regional EU area have recorded strong growth. Countries like Italy, Spain,

Sweden and the Czech Republic have seen high growth in ski sales in the recent years. Furthermore, Austria occupies a leading position within the ski production industry, as one of the most important markets with an export rate about 80%, a stable job sector and a world-wide reputation for high quality products and expertise. Austria occupies the second place world-wide with almost 400,000 sold pairs of skies. The United States is at the moment the biggest market with slightly more than 500,000 ski pairs sold in 2018 (Kleine Zeitung, 2019).

What is more, with a view to the Winter Olympics 2022, China is generally seen as a highly promising market and Chinas government started to promote winter sports and skiing to more than 300 million citizens. Previously, numerous initiatives within the DACH area to strengthen the market access, such as a cooperation agreement between the Austrian and Chinese ski associations to capture value out of the rising market in China (Wiener Zeitung, 2019).

4.4.3 Prostheses and stents

The use of medical devices like prostheses and stents is associated with considerable risk as these devices directly interact with the human body. Therefore, all medical devices must meet rigid quality standards to ensure that no unintended harm is inflicted on the patient. Coating of medical devices can help to reduce those risks and has thus lately attracted the attention of companies in the medical industry.

Figure 10 - Stent inside a blood vessel (Spiegel, 2014)

Problem description

Some of the most severe problems associated with prostheses are premature wear and dislocation in hip and knee prostheses, infection and rejection in dental prostheses, restenosis and heavy metal release in coronary stents (Garcia, Rivero, Ortiz, Quintana, & Rodriguez, 2018).

Current solutions

Different types of coating like physical vapor deposition (PVD), thermal projection or ionic implantation are currently used. PVD for example is used to coat devices with diamond-like carbon or ceramic in order to increase wear resistance and create antibacterial surfaces. The use of thermal projection of hydroxyapatite can enhance the growth of bone cells on titanium prostheses (Garcia et al., 2018).

The potential of HiPIMS

HiPIMS can greatly increase wear resistance of prostheses as it allows for coatings with high adhesion and density. Furthermore, the use of HiPIMS to create coatings with antibacterial properties consisting of a ceramic or diamond-like carbon surface doped with antibacterial elements like copper or silver can reduce the risk of infections (Garcia et al., 2018).

Dr. Schönberger, head of R&D at Urotech, also mentioned that the coating of polyurethane stents with nitinol - alloy made of nickel and titanium - might be a future application for HiPIMS. Nitinol is of high interest for manufacturers of medical devices as it has shape-memory effect properties, which means that it can return to its original shape after being deformed (Stoeckel, 1995).

Restrictions and needs for adaption

According to Garcia et al. (2018), HiPIMS is already tested in the prostheses industry and the first results are very promising. Further research, however, will be necessary on what materials can be used as target or substrate in the coating process.

Benefit relevance and strategic fit

With a score of 1,5 the Benefit relevance is high. According to Mr. Zipper and Dr. Schönberger, product marketing manager respectively head of R&D at Urotech, all of the three core benefits are relevant in the manufacturing of prostheses and stents. In addition, the relevance index is also high which is mainly due to the high relevance of the problem and the large number of people for who a solution would be relevant.

The strategic fit is also relatively high with a score of 1. Apart from market fit, which scored high due to the high market potential, all other items scored in the medium range. While prostheses for example meet the size criteria very well, stents are too small. Therefore, we assigned one of two possible points in this category.

Altogether this adds up to a high overall score of 2.5 points.

Market overview

With annual revenues of over 425 billion US Dollar in 2018, the global market for medical devices is huge and the expected growth of 5.4% annually is also considerable. Key growth drivers are the aging population, the growing prevalence of chronic diseases and the growing demand for surgical procedures. Furthermore, technological advancements and a rising demand for innovative products to overcome unmet needs in the healthcare area are considered to be factors for the growth in the medical device market within the forecast period (Fortune Business Insights, 2019).

Table 3 - Revenue medical industry from 2016 to 2023 (in Billion US Dollar) (Statista, 2018)

Both the global market for stents and the global market for prostheses is expected to grow at similar rates as the medical device industry with growth rates of 5.2% and 4% respectively. While growth in the stents market is mainly due to an increasing number of heart-related diseases and the huge demand for various diagnosis and treatment methods, the main growth drivers for the prostheses market are new surgical techniques and the rising demand for body part replacements (IndustryArc, 2019).

4.4.4 Industrial punching tools

Industrial punching tools have to endure high mechanical stress and friction. Compared to other cost factors, the cost of these tools often represents a relatively high proportion of the total cost of production. Therefore, a long service life with a maximized number of strokes is important. There is a wide range

Figure 11 - Industrial punching tool (Leicht & Müller, 2020)

of industries that rely on such tools. Applications reach from cutting glass fibre to stamping high volumes of pieces out of metal coils. Especially competitive industries with a need for efficient processes (e.g. manufacturing of hinge systems) use punching tools (Anonymous 1, 2020).

Problem description

Punching tools (stamps) wear off and have to be replaced after a certain number of produced units. The quality and precision of the manufactured goods is a crucial factor for when tools need to be replaced (Anonymous 1, 2020). The higher the required precision and wear off, the earlier they need to be replaced. Each punching tool, therefore, should endure as many strokes as possible to reduce costs. Currently cutting glass fibre faces the additional problem that coatings reduce the sharpness of the edges of the stamps. Thinner coatings could reduce this issue, lead to longer service lives and enhanced quality (Broger, 2020).

Current solutions

Currently, different types of PVD and PECVD coatings are used for punching tools. They comprise a wide range of different technologies. HiPIMS belongs to the group of PVD coatings, but no evidence has been found that it is currently used to coat punching tools.

The potential of HiPIMS

HiPIMS coatings offer better wear off resistance than the PECVD coatings (Pennsylvania State University, 2015). Since this is one of the most important properties punching tools have to meet, HiPIMS could be beneficial. Additionally, the thin layers that can be coated with HiPIMS could enhance the quality of the edges and make them sharper (Anonymous 1, 2020). This is an important factor in regard to the quality of products manufactured with punching tools.

Restrictions and needs for adaption

Restrictions could be the fact that there are already variations of HiPIMS in use by some manufacturers of punching tools. The reason for that is that many companies conduct research to enhance existing coating techniques to adapt them to their specific needs. Furthermore, they invent new names for their specific technology. Therefore, it is not clear if there are already technologies closely related to HiPIMS in use. Additionally, variations of highly sophisticated coating technologies (e.g. Cathodic Arc or Arc evaporation) with even better characteristics tailored for this use case could limit the need for HiPIMS.

Benefit relevance and strategic fit

Punching tools score 1 out of 2 in the category Benefit relevance. Especially the very thin and long-lasting coatings offer a high potential. Furthermore, the need for increased efficiency throughout all manufacturing processes to lower costs is a promising factor for HiPIMS.

The strategic fit achieves a score of 1. The size of punching tools varies, but in general the measures of the parts that need to be coated are far smaller than those of RF cavities. This fact lowers the score significantly. Additionally, the location of manufacturers of those tools do not show a perfect fit. There are producers all over the world and emerging eastern economies further develop their capabilities to make such high-quality industrial machines and goods. Nevertheless, this application field offers potential for further technological improvement of HiPIMS and a significant market potential.

Market overview

The metal stamping market is expected to reach a worth of \$299.63 billion by 2025, which implies a predicted annual growth rate of 4.2% (Grand View Research, March 2019). A deeper analysis of the highly fragmented market, the variety of industries using different forms of punching tools and a lack of market data and statistics exceeds the scope of this report. But since such tools are used for hinge systems, deep-drawing of pots, serial production of components in the automotive industry, cutting glass fibre and many kinds of forming and cutting sheet metal, there is significant market potential (Anonymous 1, 2020).

4.4.5 Food manufacturing machinery

The Global Food Processing Machinery Market shows a huge volume and steady growth rates. However, due to its impact on people's health, global regulations and quality standards are continuously increasing. Thus, new technologies to increase both, hygiene and food-safety are highly welcome and could set a new standard.

Figure 12 - Food manufacturing machine for pastries (Polin, 2020)

Problem description

One of the biggest challenges food manufacturers are currently facing is the transformation to a new state-of-the-art production line. Since manufacturing machines are very costly and the industry's competition is relatively low, many manufacturers postponed these investments as far as possible. An interview partner working at one of Austria's leading food manufacturing companies explained the consequential issue as follows: many old iron-manufacturing-machine-parts start to lose their surface. Thus, the danger of product contamination by chipping parts is high. Furthermore, another challenge within the food manufacturing industry is the continuously increasing global hygiene standards, which often require big investments by companies to be compliant (Genner, 2020).

Current solutions

After two anonymous interviews with leading technical managers of Austria's food manufacturing industry, we received the concordant statement that expensive machines have recently received new varnish for corroding parts, which is conducted as temporary solution. We have not observed any long-term plan how to overcome this problem. Moreover, at the moment the industry is trying to meet its regulations. However, what we have found out through our interviews is that firms, in fact, would like to set new, increased quality-standards, through technological improvements (Stark, 2020).

The potential of HiPIMS

Firstly, new machines coated by HiPIMS, would show extended lifetime and increased quality-safety of produced goods. Furthermore, corroding machine parts could be replaced with long-lasting HiPIMS coated parts. Secondly, HiPIMS coatings could improve the level of hygiene of every surface with food-contact. Hence, it could set a new standard for the food-manufacturing industry.

Restrictions and needs for adaption

Within the food manufacturing industry, we face numerous restrictions regarding regulations and laws. Furthermore, the global health and quality standards are increasing steadily, which in many cases cover the entire manufacturing process and thus, its machines too. Moreover, we observed specific EU-regulations about coating techniques allowed to be in touch with the food manufactured (General Food Law Regulation No 1935/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 October 2004 on materials and articles intended to come into contact with food).

Benefit relevance and strategic fit

With a score of 0.83 the Benefit relevance is relatively low. According to two anonymously conducted interviews, only one of the three core benefits is relevant in the food manufacturing industry. However, there are several other useful HiPIMS characteristics which are of great benefit for this industry, for example its attributes in bacterial inactivation. Furthermore, the big number of people who would benefit

from its added value in the food manufacturing industry leads to a slightly increased Benefit relevance of 0.83.

The strategic fit is relatively high with a score of 1.13 out of 2. Since the size criteria are met very well, the criteria of regionality are met admissibly, due to its big regional market especially within the DACH area, and eventually no restriction through prohibited application fields, we calculated one of two possible points in this category.

Altogether this adds up to an overall score of 1.96 points.

Market Overview and Data

The Global Food Processing Machinery Market was valued at \$52,787 million in 2016. The markets estimated annual growing rate is 3.9% from 2018 to 2023. Hence, the market is projected to reach almost \$69 million by 2023 (Food Processing Machinery Market, 2017).

The market data figures indicate that the year-on-year consumption & sales of processed food is steady and is estimated to grow during the forecast period resulting in growth and expansion of global food processing machinery market, especially in Asia-Pacific and Europe. Even though developed economies show mature markets, the demand is fuelled by replacement of conventional tools over advanced technology and innovative new solutions to enhance performance or level of quality and hygiene. Introduction of new technological advancements and rise in demand from emerging economies provide new opportunities for market growth (Biswa, 2017). The food processing machinery market is segmented on the basis of type, application, mode of operation, and geography. Based on type, it is classified into depositors, extruding machines, mixers, refrigeration, slicers & dicers, and others (cutting machines, dispensing machines, and ovens). The global food processing machinery market is driven by rise in demand for processed food due to preference of consumers for nutritious, hygienic, and safe food products. (Food Processing Machinery Market, 2017)

5 Conclusion & recommendations

This section is structured into three parts and provides a brief conclusion and possible next steps to further explore the potential of HiPIMS. The first aims at drawing some final conclusions and depict the most important insights. The second discusses general information regarding the data, faced issues, and possible ways to increase the value of the generated results. The third part is about industry specific recommendations and possible research questions to deepen the understanding of HiPIMS' applicability in the respective fields.

In conclusion, it can be said that HiPIMS is an innovative and highly promising technology. Its core benefits make the technology a potential successor of existing coating technologies and opens up a large number of potential application fields in various industries. Furthermore, as coating plays a key role in the production process of numerous goods, the interest for new coating technologies is high.

However, it needs to be mentioned that the diffusion of HiPIMS is currently low and many companies are not yet aware of the technology. At the same time, many companies are not willing to reveal information about their current issues, as it concerns both product and process optimization. However, the companies that decided to participate in this project, often showed considerable interest and wanted to know specific details about HiPIMS.

For this reason, a detailed report comprising all the technological aspects HiPIMS offers would increase the understanding of the technology and potential users could elaborate in detail if these coatings could potentially solve problems for them. Another important factor that should be considered for further research is that the cost of HiPIMS coatings and achievable production volumes are key aspects for potential users. Additionally, focusing on cooperation with HiPIMS machine and device manufacturers (such as CEMECON and Melec) could help with the further exploration of potential application fields.

The following industry-specific recommendations outline possible next steps to assess the potential that HiPIMS could potentially offer for the analyzed industries.

The ski industry reached the highest score with 3.17 out of 4. Coating the upper side of the ski offers potential to achieve a long-lasting change in this market. To achieve this, contacting ski producers as well as HiPIMS machine manufacturers to further elaborate the potential impact HiPIMS coatings could have on ski manufacturers is recommended. Helmut Holzer, who works at Atomic, one of the major ski producers worldwide, shows high interest and indicated his openness for further discussions. Coating wakeboards and waterskies would work similar to the coating of skis and could thus prove to be yet another application field.

The second most promising application field is medical products. In this field, the coating of stents and prostheses seem to be the most suitable one. HiPIMS could increase the durability and functionality of these devices. In a first step, it is recommended to develop an understanding of the specific regulations

regarding instruments and devices permanently implanted in human bodies. These insights can initially determine if the needed properties can be achieved with HiPIMS coatings in general.

In regard to industrial punching tools, a mapping of the variations of sputtering and plasma enhanced coating techniques would be an important first step to get an understanding of high-performance coatings. Furthermore, a benchmark analysis of these coating techniques with a strong focus on wear-off resistance and life time enhancement could exactly determine whether HiPIMS outperforms competing technologies.

To further evaluate the potential HiPIMS could offer to users of food manufacturing machines, a detailed cost analysis of current solutions and the monetary implications of hygiene problems that HiPIMS could prevent should be considered. If HiPIMS coatings could reduce the overall costs, it would provide significant value for the industry.

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manager at Urotech, about potential new application fields within the medical devices
industry.

Appendix

A List of Expert Interviews

Name	Company	Profession	Type, Date	Interview Participant	Language
Interview Key insights and notes					

SF	Samuel Fuchs				
FG	Florian Grech				
EW	Erik Wolf				
TZ	Tobias Zsilavec				

Johannes Gutleber	CERN	Project Partner	10.10.2019	SF, FG, EW, TZ	German
<p>Since Mr. Gutleber is our contact person at CERN, the video call with him was the first interview we conducted. He gave us a short presentation on CERN and their use of HiPIMS in the manufacturing of the radiofrequency cavities. Mr. Gutleber answered our remaining questions regarding the project. He provided us with a list of experts and current users of HiPIMS so that we could contact them in the initial phase of our project.</p>					

Peter Keinz	WU	Professor at WU	15.10.2019	SF, FG, EW, TZ	German
<p>Dr. Peter Keinz is deputy director of the Entrepreneurship & Innovation Institute at the Vienna University of Economics and Business Administration and a proven expert on the TCL method. The purpose of this interview was to get to know the most important features of the methodology and to understand them correctly.</p>					

Ralf Bandorf	Fraunhofer Institute	Group Leader	24.10.2019	FG, TZ	German
<p>Mr. Bandorf is a researcher at the German Fraunhofer institute. He was able to give us information on different attributes of the HiPIMS technology like the great hardness of the coating and the high refraction index. Furthermore, he explained to us how ionization of the material effects the sputtering process. According to Mr. Bandorf HiPIMS is already used by several industries and companies but the main user of this technology is currently the tool industry. In the end he gave us a number of new contacts and sent us material on the underlying principles of the HiPIMS technology.</p>					

Lars Sommerhäuser	Coating Competence Center	General Contact Person	23.10.2019	EW	German
Dr. Sommerhäuser is the general contact person of the coating competence center in Switzerland. He explained the focus of the Coating Competence Center and also scheduled the appointment with Ms. Thorwarth, the expert in this field.					

Cristian Pira	Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare Frascati	Scientist	25.10.2019	EW, TZ	English
Mr. Pira gave us a brief technical introduction and mentioned some important technological differences to other methods from his point of view. In the interview he kept focusing on the differences to existing coating methods. Moreover, he mentioned the restrictions of the technology, focusing on the needed peak of power and the cost of the power supply. Furthermore, he mentioned advantages of the HiPIMS method. His final recommendation and our key finding of the interview was to focus on “High-Value-Industries”. His argument was that with expensive products, which mostly require high production quality, the investment in the needed infrastructure is more likely to be economically rational. The advantages he mentioned are the high quality of surface, the high density of the film, the possibility of conformal coating and the fact that it also works properly with high melting point materials.					

Gerhard Eichenhofer	4A – Plasma	Founder	30.10.2019	FG, TZ	German
Gerhard Eichenhofer is the founder and owner of 4A-plasma. After telling us about the benefits of HiPIMS he also mentioned some drawbacks of the technology like the relatively high cost of the power supply unit and the rather slow deposition rate of the target material. He concluded that HiPIMS indeed is an allrounder among the different sputtering techniques but lacks a discipline in which it excels. Subsequently he gave us information about the history of the HiPIMS technique and its developers. Regarding the current users, he mentioned the tool industry and the automotive industry. He also sees high potential for HiPIMS in the medical sector.					

Günter Mark	Melec	CEO	31.10.2019	FG, TZ	German
Günter Mark is the head of the German company Melec, which develops and sells power supply units for HiPIMS machines. Because of his vast knowledge in this field Mr. Mark was able to supply us with a lot of information regarding the benefits of HiPIMS and current applications of this technology. He gave us valuable information about different types of coatings like tribological coating, biocompatible coating and hard coating. Furthermore, he also gave us information on why HiPIMS has not yet become industry standard. According the Mr. Mark the rather slow coating process is the reason why HiPIMS is not usable in mass production. Finally, he named two companies for further research.					

Michael Vogel	University of Siegen	Group Leader Coating Technology	05.11.2019	FG	German
<p>Mr. Vogel is a leading scientist on the HiPIMS technology. Because of his scientific background he was able to give us interesting information on how the ionization of the target material can influence the coating process. A high degree of ionization can benefit the surface quality of the thin film in several ways. One way is the possibility to coat complex 3D objects. Another way is the emergence of nanocrystalline structures. A third way is high hardness of the thin film. Furthermore, he confirmed that the most important user of HiPIMS currently is the tool industry.</p>					

Dorothea Fonnesu	CERN Institute	PhD Student - Superconductivity	08.11.2019	FG, EW	English
Vanessa Garcia Diaz	Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare Frascati	Early Stage Researcher	08.11.2019	FG, EW	English
Stewart Leith	University of Siegen	Research assistant	08.11.2019	FG, EW	English
<p>First, we were given a detailed description of the technology. Afterwards we got a detailed explanation about their activities while doing research about HiPIMS. Our identified benefits were confirmed and we were supported in finding the right wording. We were also informed about some companies that are already working with the technology and are interested in its further development. These recommendations were of immense importance since they provided us with many of our following interview partners.</p>					

Kerstin Thorwarth	Coating Competence Center	Team "Nanoscale Materials Science"	12.11.2019	EW	German
<p>Dr. Thorwarth is a scientist at the Coating Competence Center and has vast knowledge on coating technologies, especially about the HiPIMS technology, which she is currently working with. She was able to give us important input about the relevance of different advantages of the HiPIMS technology and told us about some specific application fields, as HiPIMS is already used in manufacturing industries. Moreover, she has confirmed that HiPIMS is already well recognized by many industries. The application fields she mentioned are smartphone cover glasses (touch screens and their protection against scratches), decorative coatings (kitchen parts, cutlery, vases), sanitary installations (taps), the automotive industry, drones and aviation technology and implants.</p>					

Peter Keinz	WU	Professor at WU	18.11.2019	FG, TZ	German
<p>The second interview with Dr. Peter Keinz had the purpose of a general follow-up and the correct formulation of the benefits. Furthermore, we discussed how customer discovery interviews should be structured and conducted.</p>					

Christoph Schiffers	CEMECON	Sale representative	20.11.2019	SF, TZ	German
<p>Mr. Schiffers is responsible for sales and distribution in the German company CEMECON. The company is a leading producer of HiPIMS coating machines and offers coating services for customers. We contacted Mr. Schiffers after having concluded the first phase of our project. Therefore, we were able to ask him whether he would agree with the benefits we had found previously. He confirmed the relevance of our findings. Subsequently he gave us valuable information about current applications in the automotive industry, the glass industry and the photovoltaic industry. According to Mr. Schiffers it is only a matter of time until HiPIMS becomes the industry standard. CEMECON for example only sold one conventional coating machine in the last two years.</p>					

Michael Sandrieser	Tumbleweed	Team lead structural & aerospace	07.01.2020	FG	German
<p>Michael Sandrieser is team lead structural & aerospace in Vienna from Team Tumbleweed and provided us with his extensive knowledge of the space industry in general and Team Tumbleweed's project in particular. Basically, coating of the individual components of the Mars robot is essential and therefore a very important part of the production process. However, as the team is still in R&D, the problem has not been addressed yet, but it is one of the big to-do's in the next steps.</p>					

Helmut Holzer	Atomic	Dir. Anticipation & Advanced Research	07.01.2020	FG, TZ	German
<p>Helmut Holzer is the director of Anticipation & Advanced Research at Atomic Austria GmbH. In this customer discovery interview we wanted to find out, if the HiPIMS technology would be useful for Atomic and the skiing industry in general. Mr. Holzer affirmed this and once again emphasized the problems of the existing solution (a film), thus illustrating for us the necessity and sense of using a coating process.</p>					

Gerold Sprachmann	Riedel Group	Managing Director	07.01.2020	FG, TZ	German
<p>Gerold Sprachmann is Managing Director of Riedel Group. He provided us with expertise in the glass industry. According to him, coating in the drinking glass industry is not regularly used and not beneficial. Though he shared his knowledge about the optical glass industry and mentioned that coating is used there regularly. Furthermore, he provided us with a contact from Swarovski, where he previously worked for a long time and where they used coating on a regular basis.</p>					

Mario Genner	Anonymous	Technical Development Manager	15.01.2020	EW	German
<p>Mario Genner is the leading technical development manager in Vienna for a company, working in the development of new food processor machines and industrial kitchens with focus on increase in efficiency, hygiene and overall performance. Mr. Genner provided us with extensive knowledge,</p>					

necessary for the planning and development of those highly innovative machines and processes. Most important insights were received regarding the high regulations in quality and hygiene standards and their management.

Gerald Holzer	HoMed	CEO	15.01.2020	FG,TZ	German
<p>Gerald Holzer is CEO and owner of HoMed, a distributor for medical devices. He gave us an insight into medical technology and its products. A coating of catheters by HiPIMS would be very interesting in principle, as a new guideline for medical devices has come into effect. Therefore, many suppliers have problems, as some of the conventional procedures do not have the necessary certification. There is currently a huge vacuum in this field. Furthermore, a coating for stents and prostheses would be conceivable.</p>					

Dr. Isabella Schmiedel	Dräxlmaier	Head of Innovation Interior	15.01.2020	TZ	German
<p>Dräxlmaier AG produces interiors for vehicles, such as door panels, on-board electronics, storage systems and instrument panels. Currently, no parts are produced that are sputtered - parts are only painted or covered with a film. Ms Schmiedel also sees little potential for a new sputtering method in the coming years, as the price pressure in the industry is very high (emergence of electric cars) and sputtering would require high investments.</p>					

Anonymous 1	Anonymous	Design Engineer	16.01.2020	SF	German
<p>The company uses punching tools in the manufacturing process of most of their products. The interviewee has great knowledge about punching tools and also lectures high school mechanical engineering students.</p> <p>He especially highlighted the resistant coatings of HiPIMS, which could be beneficial for these tools. Additionally, he mentioned that a higher number of strokes automatically lead to cost savings that are important for all manufacturers.</p>					

Markus Stark	Anonymous	Team Lead Electrical Engineering	16.01.2020	EW	German
<p>Markus Stark is the manager of the department of electrical engineering in one of Austria's biggest and most famous food manufacturer. His daily activities include managing and planning of new constructions within the food production process and its alignment to all necessary hygiene and quality standards, as well as commissions of new food processing machines. He helped us to gain a deeper awareness about the numerous regulations and requirements within the food industry, which are often enforced by law and globally standardized.</p>					

Mans Rasmussen	Aesir	Former President	17.01.2020	SF	German
<p>Mans Rasmussen is the former president of the student society Aesir at the KTH Royal Institute of Technology that builds rockets.</p> <p>As bringing weight in Earth orbit is extremely expensive, declining weight of spacecrafts is an important topic. The thin layers of HiPIMS coatings could reduce weight and therefore costs. Furthermore, Mr. Rasmussen mentioned that the hostile space environment needs extremely resistant materials. Radiation and microscopic meteorites are jeopardizing many parts of rockets. The dense and hard coatings achieved with HiPIMS could protect parts of diverse components of rockets.</p>					

Anonymous 4	Anonymous	Head of R&D	22.01.2020	FG, TZ	German
<p>The company manufactures various types of rail fasteners. At present, it is not interested in a new coating method since a new technology (zinc flake coating) was only recently introduced. Of particular importance to the company are resistance to stone chipping, chemicals and weathering. In addition, the coating must not impair the material properties and must be relatively cheap to use.</p> <p>Especially the uniform coating of three-dimensional parts (tension clamps & sleeper bolts) would be of particular benefit. The interviewee points out that any coated products would have to be tested under real conditions (salt spray test)</p> <p>The interviewee does not see any potential applications for track coating. However, a coating of switches or components in locomotives would be interesting under certain circumstances.</p>					

Franz Mayr	Magna Steyr	Head of Innovation Management	22.01.2020	FG, TZ	German
<p>Magna Steyr Engineering offers its customers comprehensive design and development services. According to Franz Mayr, coating technologies are currently used particularly frequently for transmissions and engines, as these parts need to be particularly efficient or low-maintenance. However, for cost reasons, coatings are generally only used when necessary.</p> <p>Mayr also sees potential applications in the coating of tools in particular, insofar as the technology can contribute to increasing tool life.</p> <p>Mr. Mayr believes that the technology would certainly be interesting for the company due to its advantages. However, tests would have to be carried out under realistic conditions in order to find promising application possibilities. In the case of gear wheels, for example, a coating is difficult to apply because any coating is often chipped off due to the soft base material. If the technology is ready for series production, Mr. Mayr sees potential in its future application.</p>					

Michael Broger	Aetos – Ingenieurbüro GmbH	CEO & Founder	24.01.2020	SF	German
<p>Aetos designs special machines for very specific customer needs.</p> <p>Mr. Broger gave insights about the problems of punching tools. From his point of view, the possibility to coat very thin layers could prevent too thick layers on the edges of the tools, which result in lower sharpness. This aspect is especially important when cutting glass fibre.</p> <p>Because of the wear off resistant coatings HiPIMS achieves, he could imagine using it for grippers. These components would benefit from longer service lives.</p>					

Anonymous 2	Anonymous	Production	24.01.2020	SF	German
<p>Our initial assumption that cable car pulleys could benefit from HiPIMS coatings was disproved by our interviewee. But he indicated that the rolls guiding the cables could benefit of the corrosion-resistant properties of HiPIMS coatings.</p>					

Anonymous 3	Anonymous, Skiing industry	Head of Production	28.01.2020	FG, TZ	German
<p>He is the head of Production at a ski manufacturer with over 400 employees. He confirmed that a plastic foil made of polyamide or TPU (thermoplastic polyurethane elastomers) is attached to protect the surface of the ski. He mentioned that a coating with HiPIMS seems to be very promising and would be a huge benefit.</p>					

Dr. Ingo Steingoetter	Carl Zeiss Jena	Senior Scientist	28.01.2020	FG, TZ	German
<p>Carl Zeiss Jena develops and produces lenses and other optical components. Mr. Steingoetter confirms that sputtering is already widely used to coat optical components. However, HiPIMS has not yet established itself as this technology is not able to guarantee layers with sufficient homogeneity. Especially the coating of larger targets (0.5-1m²) with very homogeneous layers could be problematic. Especially the so-called arcing could be a problem in the field of fine optics, because the sensitive parts could easily become unusable by damage.</p> <p>The possibility of coating complex structures would be of great importance for the company, as the trend is towards complicated free-form lenses. According to Mr. Steingoetter, hard coatings are also interesting. Currently, optics are coated with metal oxide, for example. Thin layers would also be an advantage. Currently, several coatings are usually applied as a layer package. According to Steingoetter, conventional sputter coating machines meet the current requirements.</p> <p>Steingoetter assumes that potential fields of application could be found especially in the coating of tools with diamond-like carbon and in the coating of architectural glass. Coating of photovoltaic cells might also be useful.</p>					

Michael Zipper / Dr. Schönberger	Urotech	Product marketing manager / Head of R&D	28.01.2020	FG, TZ	German
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Urotech GmbH develops and distributes urological disposable medical products such as catheters and drainages. Coatings in urology are mostly used to make the surfaces of plastics more body friendly. According to Michael Zipper, coatings are currently used to achieve hydrophilic surface qualities. This is particularly important for catheters because their better sliding properties make them easier to insert. Since the products manufactured are disposable items, coating costs in particular are a limiting factor. Mr. Zipper therefore does not consider an application of HiPIMS in this industry to be reasonable at this time.

Mr. Schönberger thinks that a coating of prostheses or stents might be useful. These would sometimes remain in the body of a human for a very long time and would therefore have to meet the highest quality criteria. He mentions the coating of a prosthesis with titanium or the coating of a polyurethane stent with nitinol as examples.

Ralf Bandorf	Fraunhofer Institute	Group Leader	28.01.2020	FG, TZ	German
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We contacted Mr. Bandorf to verify our current potential application fields and asked him in particular about the feasibility of the technical implementation and the realisation of these.

Günter Mark	Melec	CEO	31.01.2020	FG, TZ	German
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The aim of the second interview with Mr. Mark was to get information on the questions that came up during the final presentation. According to Mr. Mark the industrial adoption rate is still very low. Even in the tools industry, which is currently the most important user of HiPIMS, only 15-20% of all tools produced are coated using HiPIMS. Furthermore, he confirmed that the variable costs of HiPIMS are the same as with ordinary magnetron sputtering, while the cost of the power supply unit is about 30,000€. Additionally, he told us about the possibility to create transparent and water repellent coating using different materials such as silicon dioxide. Finally, he gave us feedback on the application fields we found.

B User communities

Forums	Industry	Answers	Findings
motor-talk.de	Automotive engineering	15	Pistons, shafts, cylinder tracks, interior
kletterportal.at	Mountaineering	2	Spring safety hooks, carabiners, safety devices, deflectors
taucher.net	Diving	13	Mask glasses, pneumatic tools, scuba tanks, bicycle frames
administrator.de	IT	3	Motherboards, frequency converters
engineeringclicks.com	Engineering	1	Surface of touchscreen displays
elsmar.com	Medical devices	1	Implants, stents
ebme.co.uk	Medical devices	2	Antibacterial medical devices

Table 4 - User Community Findings (Wolf, 2019)

C Insights from user communities

An important finding is that there is a great interest in the core benefits of HiPIMS in the user communities of the automotive industry. A better surface quality is seen as beneficial for nearly every part of an engine. Especially pistons, shafts and cylinders were mentioned frequently in combination with a longer service life and higher levels of efficiency and performance that could be achieved. This is consistent with the statement of C. Pira (2019) that industries with significant initial investments by consumers have a need for high quality and low maintenance effort. But the discussions show, too, that manufacturers of engines use sophisticated, reliable and tested materials and techniques, which are perfectly tailored for these use cases. In addition, the maturity of combustion engines in the automotive industry has to be taken into account. Car manufacturers are shifting their R&D expenses away from them towards sustainable alternatives. The second mentioned aspect regarding the automotive industry refers to the coating of interior parts. As decorative articles are one of the potential application fields, these findings underline the potential benefits of HiPIMS in this area. As Thorwarth (2019) emphasized the use of HiPIMS in the decorative goods industry, the case of coating interior parts is promising.

Users of diving communities pointed out that the benefits of HiPIMS could potentially be useful for scuba tanks. The tanks wear off, because of the rough environment they are permanently exposed to. The salt, tanks clashing against each other and the sand shorten their lifetime.

Medical devices also show a need for the qualities HiPIMS coatings bring with them. Devices that are implanted in human bodies permanently must have specific antibacterial characteristics and consist of materials that are compatible with the human body.

D Benefit relevance and Strategic fit calculation

Benefit relevance											
Company	Application field	Interviewee	Position	Benefit relevance	N. of rel. Benefits	Relevance index	Problem is relevant	Problem will become more important	The prevailing solution is not sufficient	The solution is important for a high number of people	
Dräxlmaier AG	Automotive	Dr. Isabelly Schmiedel	Head of Innovation Interior	0,25	1	0,75	1	0	0	2	
Anonymous	Automotive	Anonymous	Head of R&D	0,33	2	0,5	1	0	0	1	
Magna Steyr	Automotive	Franz Mayr	Head of Innovation Management	0,50	2	0,75	1	0	1	1	
Atomic	Ski	Helmut Holzer	Dir. Anticipation & Advanced R.	1,17	2	1,75	2	1	2	2	
Anonymous	Ski	Anonymous	Head of Production	1,17	2	1,75	2	1	2	2	
HoMed	Medical (Catheters)	Gerald Holzer	CEO	0,83	2	1,25	2	0	1	2	
Urotech GmbH	Medical (Catheters)	Michael Zipper	Product Marketing Manager	0,83	2	1,25	2	0	1	2	
Urotech GmbH	Medical (Catheters)	Dr. Schönberger	Head of R&D	0,83	2	1,25	2	0	1	2	
HoMed	Medical (Protheses & Stents)	Gerald Holzer	CEO	1,50	3	1,5	2	1	1	2	
Urotech GmbH	Medical (Protheses & Stents)	Michael Zipper	Product Marketing Manager	1,50	3	1,5	2	1	1	2	
Urotech GmbH	Medical (Protheses & Stents)	Dr. Schönberger	Head of R&D	1,50	3	1,5	2	1	1	2	
Anonymous	Food manufacturing	Mario Genner	Technical Development Manager	1,17	2	1,75	1	2	2	2	
Anonymous	Food manufacturing	Markus Stark	Team Lead Electrical Engineering	1,33	2	2	2	2	2	2	
Riedel Group	Glass	Gerold Sprachmann	Managing Director	0,50	3	0,5	0	0	0	2	
Team Tumbleweed	Aerospace	Michael Sandrieser	Team lead structural	0,83	2	1,25	2	2	1	0	
Aesir	Aerospace	Mans Rasmussen	Former President	0,83	2	1,25	2	2	1	0	
Aetos	Stamping tools	Michael Broger	CEO	1,17	2	1,75	2	2	2	1	
Anonymous	Stamping tools	Anonymous	Design Engineer	0,83	2	1,25	2	1	1	1	
Aetos	Gripper	Michael Broger	CEO	0,17	1	0,5	1	0	0	1	
Anonymous	Cable cars	Anonymous	Production	0,17	2	0,25	1	0	0	0	

Table 5 - Calculation of Benefit relevance (Fuchs, 2020)

Benefit relevance	
Automotive	0,36
Ski	1,17
Catheters	0,83
Protheses & Stents	1,50
Food manufacturing	0,83
Glass	0,50
Aerospace	0,83
Stamping tools	1,00
Gripper	0,17
Cable cars	0,17

Table 6 - Benefit relevance score (Fuchs, 2020)

Strategic fit								
Company	Application field	Interviewee	Position	Strategic fit	Regionality	Size	Market fit	Tech. Improvement
Dräxlmaier AG	Automotive	Dr. Isabelly Schmiedel	Head of Innovation Interior	1,25	1	1	2	1
Anonymous	Automotive	Anonymous	Head of R&D	1,50	2	1	1	2
Magna Steyr	Automotive	Franz Mayr	Head of Innovation Management	1,25	1	1	2	1
Atomic	Ski	Helmut Holzer	Dir. Anticipation & Advanced R.	2,00	2	2	2	2
Anonymous	Ski	Anonymous	Head of Production	2,00	2	2	2	2
HoMed	Medical (Catheters)	Gerald Holzer	CEO	0,75	1	0	1	1
Urotech GmbH	Medical (Catheters)	Michael Zipper	Product Marketing Manager	0,75	1	0	1	1
Urotech GmbH	Medical (Catheters)	Dr. Schönberger	Head of R&D	1,00	1	0	1	2
HoMed	Medical (Protheses & Stents)	Gerald Holzer	CEO	1,00	1	1	1	1
Urotech GmbH	Medical (Protheses & Stents)	Michael Zipper	Product Marketing Manager	1,00	1	1	1	1
Urotech GmbH	Medical (Protheses & Stents)	Dr. Schönberger	Head of R&D	1,00	1	1	1	1
Anonymous	Food manufacturing	Mario Genner	Technical Development Manager	1,25	2	2	1	0
Anonymous	Food manufacturing	Markus Stark	Team Lead Electrical Engineering	1,00	1	2	1	0
Riedel Group	Glass	Gerold Sprachmann	Managing Director	0,75	1	0	1	1
Team Tumbleweed	Aerospace	Michael Sandrieser	Team lead structural	1,00	1	1	0	2
Aesir	Aerospace	Mans Rasmussen	Former President	0,75	1	0	1	1
Aetos	Stamping tools	Michael Broger	CEO	1,00	1	0	1	2
Anonymous	Stamping tools	Anonymous	Design Engineer	1,00	1	0	2	1
Aetos	Gripper	Michael Broger	CEO	0,75	1	1	0	1
Anonymous	Cable cars	Anonymous	Production	1,00	2	1	1	0

Table 7 - Calculation of Strategic fit (Fuchs, 2020)

Strategic fit	
Automotive	1,33
Ski	2,00
Catheters	0,83
Protheses & Stents	1,00
Food manufacturing	1,13
Glass	0,75
Aerospace	0,88
Stamping tools	1,00
Gripper	0,75
Cable cars	1,00

Table 8 - Strategic fit score (Fuchs, 2020)